

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE BERRIES OF *LAVUNGO SCANDENS* (ROXB.)

BY K. K. BASIAS AND S. S. DESHPANDE

The essential oil from the berries of *Lavungo Scandens* consists of 56% cineol, 30% cinnamyl cinnamate and 9% methyl cinnamate

The plant *Lavungo Scandens* (Roxb.) Buch.-Ham exwight., known in Sanskrit as "*Lavang lala*" is indigenous to India and belongs to the family of Rutaceae. It is a stout scandent shrub of E. Bengal and Assam bearing white, very fragrant flowers, 1" in diameter and oblong berries with aromatic pulp. Neither the flowers nor the berries have been chemically examined for their aromatic constituents though the berries have been used for perfuming hair oils. They are said to be of high medicinal value, specially in curing baldness. On account of the extreme aroma they possess, they are commonly known as 'Sugandh kokila.'

The essential oil is obtained by the steam distillation of the dried berries in 2.5% yield. It has the following properties: d_{25}^{20} , 0.945; n_D^{20} , 1.5120; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, -1° ; acid value, 1.93 and ester value, 102.5.

The oil (80 c.c.) was distilled at atmospheric pressure and the following fractions were collected:

- (I) 176°—178°, 45 c.c.
- (II) 243°—245°, 25 c.c.
- (III) 261°—263°, 7 c.c.

Fraction (I) is strongly odorous and smells like camphor. It absorbs bromine and does not show any reducing properties, nor does it show the presence of any functional groups. Its boiling point and odour suggest its identity with cineol which has subsequently been confirmed. Thus, it forms a solid compound with syrupy phosphoric acid (Kebler, *Amer. J. Pharm.*, 1898, 70, 492), and a crystalline compound with resorcinol melting at 85°-87° (Baeyer and Virck, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1209). The identity of this fraction with cineol was finally confirmed by preparing resorcinol addition compound with a genuine sample of cineol obtained by us from eucalyptus oil and observing the mixed melting point of the addition products, when no depression in the melting point was observed. Amount of cineol in the oil was estimated by treating it with a 50% solution of resorcinol and decomposing the solid addition compound obtained with caustic soda, when the cineol was liberated. Estimated in this way the percentage of cineol in the oil was found to be 56%.

Fraction (II) on redistillation boils at 245° and possesses a fine pleasant fruity odour. On keeping in ice, it freezes to a white creamy solid which melts at room

temperature. It shows indifference towards reagents for alcohols, aldehydes and ketones. When heated with Fehling's solution, the latter is not reduced, but a crystalline precipitate separates which has been proved to be sodium cinnamate. The fraction was hydrolysed with alkali and the acid and alcohol separated. The acid was identified as cinnamic acid from (a) its melting point, (b) its reaction with bromine and (c) its neutral equivalent. The alcohol was identified as cinnamyl alcohol from its boiling point, and the melting point of its dibromo derivative, 74° (Grimaux, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 120). The ester is therefore cinnamyl cinnamate. This was further confirmed by preparing the dibromide of the ester which melted on recrystallisation at 151° (Gildmeister and Hoffman, "The Ethereal Oils," Vol. I, p. 646). The identity of the cinnamyl alcohol in the hydrolysis product of the ester was further confirmed by taking the mixed melting point of the bromo derivative obtained from the above alcohol and the bromo derivative prepared by us from a genuine sample of cinnamyl alcohol, when no depression was observed.

Fraction (III) boils at 263° and possesses a pleasant fruity odour like fraction (II). It also freezes on being kept in ice and melts to a liquid at room temperature. It also behaves similarly with Fehling's solution. On hydrolysis with alkali it forms a clear solution in water indicating that this fraction is an ester of cinnamic acid with some alcohol which is soluble in water. Among the naturally occurring esters of cinnamic acid, the possibility of methyl cinnamate suggests itself. This boils at 263° and freezes at 33° . The alcohol formed on hydrolysis of fraction (III) could not be isolated on account of its solubility in alcohol. The identity of methyl cinnamate in this fraction was confirmed by preparing the bromo derivative which melted after recrystallisation at 117° . It was further confirmed by taking the mixed melting point of the two bromo derivatives, one obtained from the ester present in fraction (III) and the other, prepared from a genuine sample of methyl cinnamate. No depression was observed in the melting point.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Essential Oil.—The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of the berries from a copper still fitted with a spiral copper condenser. The oil separated from the aqueous distillate as a light yellow layer floating over water. It was separated from water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. It gave the properties as shown above.

TABLE I

Fraction No.	Boiling range.	Vol.	Yield.	Properties.
I.	176° - 178°	45 c.c.	56%	Addition product with phosphoric acid and also with resorcinol, m. p. 85° - 87° .
II.	243° - 245°	25	30	Dibromo addition product, m. p. 151° . Freezes to a creamy solid on cooling.
III.	261° - 263°	7	9	Solidifies on cooling to a white creamy solid; bromo-derivative, m. p. 117° .
Loss		3		

Fractionation of the Oil.—The oil (80 c.c.) on distillation at atmospheric pressure gave the following fractions, whose boiling points, boiling ranges, percentage yields and properties are shown in Table I.

Identification of Cineol in Fraction (I): Addition Compound with Phosphoric Acid.—The fraction (5 c.c.) was cooled in ice and salt and syrupy phosphoric acid (2 c.c., d 1.75) was gradually added with constant stirring. The solid addition compound separated and became harder on further cooling.

Cineol-resorcinol Addition Compound.—To the fraction (5 c.c.) was added resorcinol (1 g.) and the mixture warmed until resorcinol went into solution. On cooling, addition product separated in rhombic plates. On filtering, washing a little with alcohol, and drying the compound it melted at $80-85^{\circ}$. On recrystallisation its melting point rose to $85-87^{\circ}$. Mixed melting point of this compound with the one prepared from a genuine sample of cineol showed no depression.

Estimation of Cineol in the Oil—To 20 c.c. of the oil was added a 50% solution of resorcinol and the mixture shaken well, when a solid addition compound separated. It was filtered and then decomposed with caustic soda solution when cineol was liberated. It was extracted with ether and after removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was distilled. It measured about 11.3 c.c. The percentage of cineol in the oil is thus 55.9% which agrees with the distillation figures.

Identification of Cinnamyl Cinnamate in Fraction (II): Hydrolysis.—A mixture of the fraction (10 c.c.) and a 10% solution of caustic soda (30 c.c.) was refluxed for 3 hours. On cooling, the products of hydrolysis separated into two layers. The layers were separated and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with hydrochloric acid, when an acid separated which on recrystallisation from hot water melted at 133° and showed no depression in melting point when mixed with a genuine sample of cinnamic acid. It absorbed bromine. (Found: Neutral equiv., 148.5. $C_9H_8O_2$ requires neutral equiv., 148).

The ethereal extract was washed with water until free from alkali and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid distilled at 255° . A bromo compound was prepared by adding bromine to a solution of the alcohol in chloroform until no more of it was decolorised. A solid compound separated after two days, which melted after recrystallisation from alcohol at 72° . A mixed melting point of this bromo compound with the bromo compound prepared from a pure and genuine sample of cinnamyl alcohol showed no depression.

Bromine Addition Product of Cinnamyl Cinnamate.—To the fraction (2 c.c.) was added bromine (1 c.c.), dissolved in ether, and the mixture cooled in a freezing mixture. After 24 hours, crystalline dibromo addition compound separated. On recrystallisation from chloroform it melted at 151° . (Found: Br, 37.5. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_2Br_2$: Br, 37.7 per cent).

Identification of Methyl Cinnamate in Fraction (III).—Fraction (III) was hydrolysed like fraction (II) and cinnamic acid in it was identified. The hydrolysis product was a

clear, homogeneous solution unlike as in fraction (II). A part of it was distilled until about one third distilled over. The aqueous distillate on heating with potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid evolved vapours smelling like formaldehyde, suggesting the possibility of methyl alcohol in the distillate.

A bromo compound was prepared by adding bromine to an ethereal solution of the fraction till the colour of bromine persisted. On shaking and keeping for some time a thick crystalline compound separated. On recrystallisation from alcohol it melted at 117° . Mixed melting point of this compound with the bromo compound prepared from a genuine sample of methyl cinnamate showed no depression. (Found: Br, 49.3. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_2Br_2$: Br, 49.6 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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